

CONDITION OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM ON THE BACKGROUND OF CORONAVIRUS INFECTION IN CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10776299>

Abstract:

In December 2019, the world became aware of an epidemic of a very severe infection caused by a new coronavirus. Later, WHO declared a pandemic. The pediatricians were ready for the worst. The novel infection was expected to promptly spread among the most vulnerable population, children. But the clinicians soon understood that the situation is unbelievable: adults develop severe disease and die, while the children remain almost excluded from the infection spreading. 9 months have passed in the “new reality”.

The humankind was learning to respond to the new infection challenge by empirical search for the potential therapeutic and diagnostic solutions and conducting wide clinical studies in parallel. A few questions have been answered because of consolidated and/or isolated actions of researchers and clinicians at the national, regional, and international levels. However, most aspects of how the new coronavirus affects the humans, including children, is still unclear and our knowledge of these aspects cannot be transferred in the routine practice. This review presents latest understanding of the course of the novel coronavirus infection in children, its treatment and outcomes.

Keywords: Covid-19, children, cardiovascular system.

Purpose of the work: To determine the degree of impact of COVID-19 on the cardiac vascular system and the clinical course of children who were treated in a specialized hospital (Children's Clinical Hospital No. 3 of the city of Tashkent) for the treatment of patients with coronavirus infection.

Material and research methods. We conducted a retrospective analysis of the medical records of 86 children of various ages who were hospitalized with a confirmed diagnosis of the new coronavirus infection COVID-19 for September – November 2020. All patients underwent clinical, anamnestic, functional studies (radiography and computed tomography of the chest) and laboratory tests.

Research results: Among the main symptoms of COVID-19 in sick children are fever, cough, and a feeling of shortness of breath (shortness of breath, rapid breathing). Less common were myalgia, anorexia, nausea, weakness, sore throat, nasal congestion, and headache. Most developed symptoms within 2 days or by the 14th day after contact with the sick person. The results obtained suggest that viral infections can provoke the development of arrhythmias, decompensated

heart failure, and thromboembolic complications mainly due to a combination of a significant systemic inflammatory response and localized inflammation of the vascular wall. COVID-19 is no exception in this regard, which is likely to change the clinical manifestations of current CVDs and lead to the development of additional life-threatening complications.

Analysis of the results showed that viral infection and virus-induced immune reactions in most cases underlie the inflammatory process in myocarditis. Activated macrophages and other cells of the immune system attract T- and B-lymphocytes to the site of inflammation through the production of chemokines. The latter implements the mechanisms of cell-mediated cytotoxicity and ensures the production of antiviral antibodies - the mechanism of apoptosis of cardiomyocytes is triggered with further systolic dysfunction of the myocardium.

The data studied showed that of 86 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of COVID-19, 27.8% developed acute cardiovascular complications leading to cardiac dysfunction and rhythm disturbances. In the patients studied, myocarditis often manifests itself as cardiac arrhythmias with symptoms of progressive heart failure at any stage of the disease. The first manifestations of myocarditis include weakness, increased fatigue, myalgia, and occasionally low-grade fever, which are not caused by myocardial damage itself, but by the manifestation of an infectious inflammatory process.

Conclusions. Children with COVID-19 and cardiovascular comorbidity are at high risk of developing septic shock, which can be fatal. Acute cardiac dysfunction as a predictor of poor prognosis in patients with COVID-19. As the disease spreads and new data becomes available, it is prudent to determine risk factors for cardiovascular complications in these patients. It is possible that maintaining a register of patients with COVID-19 and systematically recording clinical parameters, cardiovascular and other complications will make it possible to determine the current characteristics of patients, approaches to treatment, and prevention to develop a risk model for complications.

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